

The Geopolitical Construction of Space: Ceuta and Melilla

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Abstract

The Moroccan-Spanish geopolitical relations have witnessed several ebbs and flows. They have gone through different stages that have conditioned and limited their cooperation and outweighed their competition. These stages include the Andalusian period, the post-Andalusian era, Spanish colonization, and the post-colonial preservation of Moroccan occupied enclaves and islands. Each of these periods contributed their share to the deterioration in interstate relations between these two strategic neighboring countries that are full of qualifications and competences in almost every aspect of life. Benevolent governance on both shores could surely do wonders to the common good of the two peoples as they both reside strategic locations on the world map.

Keywords: Morocco; Spain; geopolitical contention; Ceuta; Melilla.

1. Introduction

The geopolitical and diplomatic relations between Spain and Morocco have always been of paramount importance. The Andalus, as a contact zone between two cultures, two religions, two ideologies, and two rival powers, was the most significant pinnacle of the competitive geopolitical construction of how the two sovereign states perceive themselves in the 21st century. “Moorish Spain” or the Islamic presence in the Iberian Peninsula, for almost eight centuries (711-1492), was an era that formulated the matrix of Islamic-Christian sociopolitical and economic relationships in general, and the Moroccan-Spanish geopolitical rivalry in particular. The unfolding of the Islamic religion to the peninsula was of great importance as it was the first hegemonic form of power relations between the Islamic and the Christian world. After several ebbs and flows of Hispanic resistance, political, economic, and military changes took place. Thus, the Umayyad Hispania was to inaugurate a new chapter in world history that constituted a very crucial stage in the geopolitical fusion between “East” and “West”.

The geopolitical construction of space in the Moroccan-Spanish power relations mostly revolves around the matrix of the Andalusian Islamic “enlightened-era” as paralleled with the West European “dark ages”, medieval period (from the 5th until the 15th centuries). During this period of European impairment, the European blown candles were to be rekindled, first from the Muslim presence on the Christian land, and second, from the willingness to take revenge of the “Moors”, and to expel them beyond the Mediterranean. What enhances such contention here is, first, the occupation of the Moroccan coastal enclaves and islands like Ceuta and Melillia, Chafarinas Islands, Perejil Island (Laila Island), and Badis and Nekkorr, right after the expulsion of Muslims from Al-Andalus and the destruction of The Nasrid Kingdom of Granada (the last Islamic state in the Iberian peninsula (1232-1492))¹.

Second, setting these enclaves, especially Ceuta and Melilla, as watch islands/watchtowers, serving both as a preemptive strategy to deter any kind of possible Moroccan expansion to the west and as a reminder of the expulsion or revenge of the “Moorish” presence in the Andalus. The conquest of Melilla took place in the the 15th century (1497) by Spain and the conquest of Ceuta in the 15th century by Portugal (1415) then it “was transferred to Spain under the Treaty of Lisbon in 1668”.²

Another important episode in the Moroccan-Spanish geopolitical relations was the Spanish colonial period (1912-1956), or what the French and Spanish regimes like to call “the French protectorate” and “the Spanish protectorate” over Morocco. Spanish colonialism over Northern Morocco, especially in the Rif region, was very brutal; it was one of the first powers to use internationally banned chemical weapons against civilians (after World War I) and many other humanitarian crimes. In addition to the occupation of Northern Morocco, the enclaves of Ceuta and Melilla, and other Moroccan islands, Spain also occupied the Moroccan Sahara. However, despite its compelled withdrawal from Morocco, Spain continued to preserve the two main enclaves, Ceuta and Melilla after Morocco’s independence in 1956. What is evident in the present status quo is that both countries are trying to preserve their cooperative relations as neighboring sovereign states, and at the same time, to exert their influences in the geopolitical construction of space. This is evident on the part of Spain whose foreign policy has been trying hard to set hurdles for the Moroccan diplomatic success in gaining the international community’s support in what concerns the Moroccan Western Sahara.

2. Historical background

Thanks to their distinct geostrategic positions, Morocco and Spain have always played special roles in connecting the African and European continents. The shortest

distance between Morocco and Spain along the Strait of Gibraltar, which is around 12 miles, is very suggestive of the kind of relations that could render them either cooperative or competitive. Historically, the strait served well in bridging the space between cultures, economies, religions, and interests of these neighboring geographical entities. The constructed ideological stigmas of the polarities of “Europe” and “Africa”, “East” and “West”, “North” and “South”, the “Occident” and the “Orient”, have always been present in such a continental proximity. By all the odds, spacial proximity can be either a grace or a curse. For Spain, and Europe as well, the “curse” started when “The Arabs came to the Peninsula as fanatical worshippers of Allah and of Mohammed his prophet, at whose bidding and under whose spell they found themselves embarked on a career of conquest aimed at winning all mankind for Islam: peacefully if possible, the prophet had taught, by the sword if necessary”.³ For Morocco, the curse started first with the annexation of the two Moroccan cities Ceuta and Melilla as parts of the Spanish – and later European – territories, and second, with the Spanish colonization of northern and southern Morocco.

Undoubtedly, the Muslim conquest of the Iberian Peninsula was one of the most tragic “predicaments” for the Spaniards and Europeans alike. It was very bad for them because, as Christians, they refused the presence of another religion that would certainly “threaten” their Christendom. As a faith, Islam was very strong in the hearts of its followers. After the death of the Prophet (PBUH) and “During the life time of the first caliph or successor, Palestine, Egypt, and Persia had already been overrun and added to the faith. Less than a century would suffice to carry it east to the borders of India and west over the extent of north Africa until it confronted Christian Europe across a narrow twelve miles of sea”.⁴ The fast spread of the new religion from India to Europe in less than a century, and before the discovery of the Americas by

Columbus, was like conquering the entire world. This constituted both a real predicament, and a challenge at the same time, for Christians all over the globe.

In his *Moorish Spain*, the English historian Richard Fletcher described the Muslim arrival to the peninsula at the beginning of the 8th century AD. Thus, he wrote, in 711 a Berber army led by Arabs reached the Straits of Gibraltar from Morocco, continuing a series of raids that had been underway for some time. The army was led by a general named Tariq, who is claimed to have named his landfall on the northern side of the Straits for himself: Jebel Tariq, or "the Rock of Tariq," Gibraltar. The subsequent year, a fight took place between the conquerors and the Spanish army led by King Roderic or Rodrigo, and Tariq's forces were victorious. King Roderic was assassinated, and the invaders went on to conquer Toledo, the capital city. The entire peninsula was at their feet within a few years.⁵

In the same vein, the American writer Louis L'Amour wrote describing the Islamic golden age and the expansion of the Muslim rule after the death of the Prophet (PBUH). He noted that within a hundred years, following Mohammed's death in 632, the Arabs had managed to carry the sword of Islam from the Atlantic to the Indian Ocean, controlling at one time most of Spain, part of southern France, the island of Sicily, all of North Africa and Egypt, all of Arabia, the Holy Land, Armenia, Persia, Afghanistan, and nearly a third of India. The Arab empire was broader than that of Alexander the Great of Rome.⁶

The Islamic golden age, which was undoubtedly a period of cultural, scientific, and economic flourishing, was paralleled by European decadence. This period contributed a lot to the formation of the "Moorish" character and helped in the formation and in the ideological construction of "the dangerous other". It generated countless negative reactions towards Muslims and their "potential danger". Unquestionably, the construction of the geopolitical spaces, the construction of

binaries were formulated during this period along with a set of stereotypes about Muslims. Most of these stereotypes and ideological constructions have been energized during the amalgamation of the events in Al-Andalus; the fact that pushed Spanish Catholicism⁷ to commit different brutal actions to cause problems especially between Muslims and Jews so as to demonize the “Moors” and help in their dissociation and expulsion.

However, unlike what has been imaginatively projected about the Muslim conquest of Spain and the fanatical destruction and fundamentalism that was hovering over the Christian land, Muslims proved very tolerant towards both Christians and Jews. In her book, *The Ornament of the World: How Muslims, Jews, and Christians Created a Culture of Tolerance in Medieval Spain*, the Cuban writer, María Rosa Menocal, tells the story of how Muslims, Jews, and Christians could forge a common tolerant cultural identity regardless of their sociocultural and religious differences. She refers to the tragic “massacre of Jews in Granada in 1066, while ascribing it entirely to fundamentalist Berbers, which is not wholly convincing”.⁸ More than that, “The Jews and Christians of Muslim Andalucía flourished economically and culturally under the Umayyads, whose dynasty had been transplanted from Damascus to Cordoba by the audacious Abd al-Rahman.”⁹ Seemingly, Christians, whose land had been conquered by Muslims, were deaf to whatever tolerance, scientific, cultural, and economic flourishing Muslims had achieved. What mattered most for them was the banishment of everyone and everything that is Arab/Arabic and Moorish; because as Harold Bloom clarified, “For the Jews and Moors it meant permanent exile from what had been ‘a first-rate place’; for the Old Christians it meant their triumph and their Golden Age.”¹⁰ And, that is exactly what clarifies their destruction of many libraries and thousands of books in Spain.

Undoubtedly, the tragic massacre of Jews in Granada in 1066 and the countless atrocities that were committed by the Spanish Catholics were among the preparations and the strategies of *the reconquest*. In her last chapter, epilogue: “Andalusian shards”, Menocal asks some pertinent questions about the expulsion of Muslims and Jews from Al-Andalus, she tries to understand,

“What happened? How and why does a culture of tolerance fall apart? How did a people come to abandon a culture rooted in an ethic of yes and no, so readily able to love and embrace the architecture or the poetry of political enemies or religious rivals, so willing to read good books regardless of the library they come from?”¹¹

As a logical answer for her questions, she writes, “All the answers are themselves bundles of contradictions”.¹²

Another very important period in the Morocco-Spain diplomatic and geopolitical relations is the post-Andalusian era. Islam as a tolerant religion and a hosting culture has so many things to contribute to the international community and to humanity. The tolerance and coexistence Muslims, Christians, and Jews cherished in Al-Andalus proves the relevance of the Islamic paradigm in the Iberian Peninsula and, of course, in the current polycentric world. However, after the fall of the Islamic empire in Spain and the rise of the Spanish empire that set off towards the New World, determined to explore what is beyond the vast ocean, a new era had already started. The new era or the post-Andalusian era molded the onset of Western colonialism that afflicted the world with woes and tragedies from the 15th to the 20th centuries.

Unlike the Islamic paradigm that cultivated tolerance and coexistence among the different ethnic groups and religions in the peninsula, the western paradigm alluded to “the clash of civilization” that was supposed to reign the post-cold war era in

Huntington's analysis in *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*. As a kind of response, in *Freedom and Orthodoxy: Islam and Difference in the Post-Andalusian Age*, Anouar Majid argues that the "clash of civilizations" is caused not essentially by world religion belief systems or cultural incongruities, but by the unyielding and hegemonic universalisms that have characterized world history since 1492. That is, the comprehensive worldviews of Euro-American ideologies have resulted in the marginalization of Islam and other non-European traditions, as well as an increase in suspicion, fear, and terror.¹³

In fact, Majid's theory of the "inflexible and hegemonic universalisms that have characterized world history since 1492" does apply hugely to the Moroccan-Spanish geopolitical relations. Moroccan people, especially in the Rif Region, have suffered uncountable atrocities due to the Spanish use of internationally banned chemical and biological weapons. Thus, despite the signing of the Geneva Protocol in 1925 prohibiting the use of biological and chemical weapons during international conflicts, the Spanish army used chloropicrin, mustard gas, diphosgene, and phosgene, and this was the first time chemical warfare was used after World War I.¹⁴ The collective memory in Al-Hoceima and the suburbs is still recounting these tragedies from generation to generation as people are still dying of cancer and other diseases. The Spanish army committed unforgiven brutalities and crimes towards civilians by "raping Moroccan prisoners of war, castration and mutilation, the bombing of children and women"¹⁵, and the bombing of markets and populated areas. On this basis, we can say that Spanish/European colonialism will always remain a stone in the shoe of any kind of compromise between the two countries.

What confirms the impossibility of any kind of compromise between Spain and Morocco in the future, or the disingenuous/untruthful compromises on the part of Spain, is the frivolity of the Spanish government to preserve the two Moroccan

enclaves and other coastal islands after the independence. In fact, these tails of colonialism will always remain a dark spot on the Moroccan map and a place of contention between the two neighbouring countries.

3. A geopolitical context

Geography is about power. Although often assumed to be innocent, the geography of the world is not a product of nature but a product of histories of struggle between competing authorities over the power to organize, occupy, and administer space. Imperial systems throughout history, from classical Greece and Rome to China and the Arab world, exercised their power through their ability to impose order and meaning upon space.

—Ó Tuathail, 1996

Gearóid Ó Tuathail inaugurated his work, *Critical Geopolitics: the politics of writing Global Space*, in these ideologically significant words. Undoubtedly, geography has always been a point of contention and competition between the peoples of the world. People have always been engaged in wars and conflicts that may last for years, if not centuries, to preserve a geographical entity that is considered as national, and which is always thought of in socio-political, religious and ideological terms. In this sense, a geographical entity must remain socio-politically and religiously intact and sovereign. The fact that geography, as a physical space, represents different forms and modes of power, a “product of histories”, of competition, of “imperial systems”, and of imposing “order and meaning” is very revealing. It is revealing in the sense that geography represents both space and time. Every spatial element is meaningful in terms of both physicality and temporality. There is always a complementarity between physicality and historicity in constituting visions and versions about a certain space. Thus, the interference of politics in geography makes the latter dynamic and in perpetual motion, usually, in accordance with the matrix of global

powers that never cease crafting their political presence over the national and international systems, alike.

In this context, Ceuta and Melilla should serve as good examples of how colonial and imperial systems “exercised their power through their ability to impose order and meaning upon space” as argued by Ó Tuathail. Obviously, the two Moroccan occupied enclaves have been geopolitically constructed to serve Spain’s geopolitical and geostrategic considerations. Geographically, both towns are undeniably located on the African continent. Yet, Melilla has been in Spanish possession since 1497, when it was captured by Pedro de Estopián, an envoy of the Duke of Medina Sidonia, and is one of multiple fortresses or presidios which were founded along the coast to thwart further invasions of the Spanish peninsula by the 'Moors' (the general term used to refer to the Arabs and Berbers from the south), who had subsequently been exiled five years earlier after spending around eight centuries there. Following the end of the union between Spain and Portugal in 1640, Ceuta, which had been under the Portuguese control since 1415, was formally transferred to Spain under the Treaty of Lisbon in 1668.¹⁶

In fact, the geopolitical imperative of organizing, occupying, and administering space has gone even further with the occupied towns. Spain has always sought to guarantee Europe’s backup to impose order and meaning on the colonially annexed territories, which lay beyond the sea, beyond its territory. These regions have well-established links with Europe as part of Spain, with their own elected representatives in the national Parliament, but following Spain's entry into the European Community in 1986, they became European by treaty: the majority of their citizens are Spanish, and thus now citizens of the European Union. They elect MPs to the European Parliament, and there are enormous signboards proclaiming each to be a 'Municipality of Europe' on the outskirts of both cities.¹⁷

Historically, Europe owes a lot to Spain; the Spanish Empire was the first to inaugurate the European age of exploration, especially during the early modern period. For John Julius Norwich, Spain was an exceptional case in this regard. Ferdinand and Isabella were significant for a number of reasons, including their destruction of the Kingdom of Granada, their mass expulsions of Muslims and Jews, which had a significant impact on western Europe's demography, and their sponsorship of Columbus, the first step in the Mediterranean's depreciation to the relative backwater it would become in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries.¹⁸ Of course, the Spaniards did not accomplish all of this on their own, as William S. Multby argues. Capital was provided by Genoese and German bankers. The Spanish fleet was augmented by ships and crews from various countries, and Spain's European armies were multinational in every sense of the word. Many aspects of war and administration were dominated by Castilians, but they were too few and their country was too poor to create such a global enterprise without help.¹⁹

Thus, for the sake of understanding the geopolitical construction of these physical spaces, it is necessary to put it in a global context. As an approach, geopolitics brackets the study and interaction of geography and politics. Such interaction may take the form of geographical factors that influence certain spaces and political imaginations that may orient state decisions and, thus, statecraft in general. In this vein, introducing a definition of geopolitics is worth considering here. For Agnew, “the term is now used freely to refer to such phenomena as international boundary disputes, the structure of global finance, and geographical patterns of election results”.²⁰ A more specific meaning of geopolitics refers to the “examination of the geographical assumptions, designations and understandings that enter into the making of world politics.”²¹ Geopolitics, as a field of study, was first introduced by the Swedish political scientist Rudolf Kjellén in 1899. But in terms of use, it was till

the 1930s that a group of German political geographers, particularly the retired Major General Dr Karl Haushofer in association with Adolf Hitler through Rudolf Hess that the concept was brought to the world's attention. Hitler who represented the Nazi party (1930s and 1940s) fortified his lines and consolidated his power with all obsession to expand Germany's living area.²² Undoubtedly, Hitler's conception of geopolitics was different from its being a serious field of inquiry, a method of explaining world politics; it was in fact a strategy to dominate and conquer.

However, after World War II, geopolitics started to take its shape as a serious field of inquiry. It had been a considerable ideological field for Hitler to promote his propaganda and Nazi ideology on a wider scale. Yet, things took another path, especially with "the shifting economic and geopolitical foundations of the world economy since the Second World War."²³ After the war, geopolitics was conceived of as a field of investigation necessary for every state to study its potential as a sovereign state and the potential of other states, on the one hand, and to prepare for preventive and preemptive self-defence, on the other. This stance dominated the world's political arena, especially with the emergence of USA as a world power.

The American geopoliticians, mainly Alfred Thayer Mahan, Sir Halford Mackinder, Henry Kissinger, and Zbigniew Brzezinski, wrote in excess about the American domestic and foreign policy. Mahan wrote his famous book *The Influence of Sea Power Upon History, 1660-1783*, in which he focuses on the role of the sea in terms of "use and control"²⁴ as a source of power. Mackinder's Heartland Theory constitutes a response to Mahan's *Sea Power*. While Mahan focuses on sea power, Mackinder focuses on 'the geography of the earth as being divided into the "World Island" which comprises Eurasia and Africa; and the "Peripheral Islands" which include the Americas, Australia, Japan, the British isles, and Oceania.²⁵

In his turn Kissinger, a security adviser, wrote his book about *Diplomacy* (1994) after the Cold War. His argument is that despite the fact that we are living a post-Soviet era, Russia, along with Germany, still constitutes a threat for the USA. He maintains that “unless America was organically involved in Europe, it would be obliged to involve itself later under circumstances far less favourable to both sides of the Atlantic.”²⁶ Seemingly, “it is in no country’s interest that Germany and Russia should fixate on each other as either principal partner or principal adversary. If they become too close, they raise fears of condominium; if they quarrel, they involve Europe in escalating crises.”²⁷ What is evident for Kissinger is that, “without Europe, America could turn, psychologically as well as geographically and geopolitically, into an island off the shores of Eurasia.”²⁸

Brzezinski argues for the same point. For him the “American foreign policy must remain concerned with the geopolitical dimension and must employ its influence in Eurasia in a manner that creates a stable continental equilibrium, with the United States as the political arbiter.”²⁹ The role of USA as an external arbiter, a global watch-dog, is very telling, especially for Eurasia that constitutes the “World Island” in Mackinder’s words. Thus, Eurasia (mainly Asia), the cradle of civilizations, of religions, of histories, of sciences, and the continent where the orient and the occident merge, is reduced to a mere American chessboard. Consequently, Eurasia is considered as a “chessboard on which the struggle for global primacy continues to be played, and the struggle involves geostrategy—the strategic management of geopolitical interests”.³⁰

Giving examples from an American geopolitical context is just for the sake of limiting a little bit the scope of the geopolitical analysis. A brief analysis then would suffice, because USA is today’s superpower; so, it is useful to contextualize the geopolitical contention between Morocco and Spain. This would surely help us grasp

how the geopolitical machine functions. The American recognition of the Moroccan sovereignty over Moroccan Western Sahara is very vexing to Spain, and some other countries, because the Spanish government became aware of the loaded messages the US is sending. Morocco has fully understood that these times are very tough; one single state cannot survive in a world of alliances and coalitions. One cannot do without firmly positioning his feet in a solid ground for mutual interests.

Undoubtedly, geopolitics is criticised for not being able to deal with all the factors that furnish the scene of international relations.³¹ Yet, as a method of analysis, an approach to the struggles over power and space, it should be furnished by different discourses that cover and touch upon a wide range of socio-political, economic, religious and ideological factors. Geopolitics has always been accompanied by different discourses. Accordingly, “geopolitics is defined as a discursive practice by which intellectuals of statecraft ‘spatialize’ international politics and represent it as a ‘world’ characterized by particular types of places, peoples and dramas”.³² In *Critical Geopolitics*, Agnew refers to three discourses or modes of representation (the three ages of geopolitics): civilizational geopolitics (1815-75), naturalized geopolitics (1875-1945), and ideological geopolitics (1945-90), respectively.³³ In every stage, he highlights the periodization of geopolitical discourse.

Nobody can deny the fact that there is a close relationship between the political discourse and the geopolitical reorganization of world politics and space. The geopolitical reorganization of world politics is based on crafting the political presence, especially of superpower(s), over the international system, past and present. Discourse takes different forms and modes. In this case, geopolitical discourse has the tendency to set as many varied ‘assumptions’, ‘designations’, and ‘understandings’ as is possible for its survival and maintenance. For example, the current geopolitical assumptions and designations all revolve around the slogans of

‘security’, ‘terrorism’, ‘climate change’, ‘weapons of mass destruction’, ‘resources scarcity’, ‘hegemonic annexations of different geographical entities against people’s free will’, etc. This leads to geopolitical tension and competition. In fact, this race to gain power, to gain access to vital natural resources on the regional or global scales, under different pretexts, hinders every attempt to promote dialogue and peace in various parts of the world.

Spain is very cautious in retaining good relationships with Morocco, especially on the level of political discourse; however, in what concerns the geopolitical reorganization of space they have built 6 meters high fences around the occupied enclaves, a land that Morocco has never ceased claiming as part of our nation. Obviously, there is a huge gap between abstract political discourse, and the geopolitical manipulation of space as praxis. In this context, Peter Gold notices that the fences that surround the Spanish enclaves of Ceuta and Melilla are an effort to manipulate the upsurge of Africans into Europe, even if they only divert a portion of the flow elsewhere. They are, however, a blatant and true reminder of the cultural, political, and economic barriers that Europe and its Mediterranean neighbours still have to overcome. As long as these intangible barriers exist, the enclaves will continue to serve as a conduit for migrants fleeing North Africa and elsewhere to reach Europe.³⁴ The cultural, political, and economic barriers (fences) that Spain has set is a unique ideological construction of space the 21st century has witnessed; a true reminder/remnant of the European colonialist legacy.

Geopolitics is a key element in understanding international relations. The concept sets a fertile ground for the question of international relation. It offers both a lucid and an ambiguous context in dealing with this issue. On the one hand, its lucidity resides in how the combination of politics and geography renders it possible for us to understand and deal with perceptible components in the process of international

relations such as the zones of political and economic power that are enrooted and controlled in certain geographical spaces. For example, when we talk about the USA or Europe we understand their political influence in the global decision-making, as main factors. We can also speak of rising powers such as India, China, Russia and Brazil, and how they are increasing and maintaining their economic, military and political statuses on the world's political arena. Another example is that of states that might be considered as failed or rogue states but still influence regional and global geopolitical decisions and are exploited by economically and militarily powerful states to secure their interests and privileges. The phrase "rogue state", as Noam Chomsky clarifies in his *Rogue States: The Rule of Force in World Affairs*, has two meanings: a propagandistic one that refers to various enemies, and a literal one that refers to states that refuse to abide by international conventions. Logic says that unless they are internally restrained, the most powerful regimes should fall into the latter category, which history confirms.³⁵

On the other hand, its ambiguity springs from the endless and recurring factors that never stop manipulating and influencing international relations, mainly ideological factors. The geopolitical considerations, in this sense, are always conditioned by certain interests and hidden agendas. For example, a powerful state or a confederation of states may pretend to be aiming at liberating a certain society from the shackles of tyranny, as was the case with Iraq and many other countries, while in fact they are aiming at things ranging from natural resources to their political fantasies. Therefore, if we take the concept of geopolitics as "the study of the influence of geographical factors on state behavior- how location, climate, natural resources, population, and physical terrain determine a state's foreign policy options and its position in the hierarchy of states"³⁶ we realize how fertile and crucial this

concept for a deep and founded understanding of the issue of interstate contentions, regional integrity, and global communication is.

It is crucial and fertile in the sense that it conjures very controversial issues such as human rights, global justice, sovereignty, communicative ethics, international law, environment, natural resources, etc. All these factors contribute to the geopolitical competitions between individual nations or groups of nations in the form of alliances of different states and groups on the ground of sharing common ideological interests.

The geopolitical contention over space between Morocco and Spain, as I mentioned above in this section, dates back to the Andalusian era. Many historians, sociologists, and politicians agree that this period constituted and molded irreconcilable attitudes and prejudices among Muslims and Christians. For instance, the former Spanish Prime Minister José Maria Aznar sees that the conflict between the two countries began in the eighth century. In a lecture given at Georgetown University on September 21, 2004, Aznar stated that Spain's long battle against terrorism began in 711, when Muslims led by Tariq Ibn Ziyad invaded the country. He went on to say that the terrorist attacks in Madrid on March 11, 2004, had nothing to do with the Iraqi crisis and had everything to do with the fall of Al-Andalus.³⁷ Thus, overlooking the fact that Morocco had been exposed to the same brutal terrorist attacks on May 16, 2003, in Casablanca, and in which about 45 people were killed. Others, like Anouar Majid, believe that the true predicament of the geopolitical contention between these two nations started during the post-Andalusian era.

Generally speaking, and for the sake of comparing the Muslim rule in Al-Andalus to the Spanish one in some parts of Morocco, we can say that, Spain, enjoyed all sorts of economic, cultural, and scientific flourishing during the Muslim presence on the Iberian Peninsula. Christians and Jews lived in harmony and tolerance under the

Muslim presence; while Moroccans suffered woes and tragedies under the Spanish colonialism and they are still suffering the remnants of the chemical and biological weapons in Northern Morocco along with the preservation of parts of the Moroccan land.

4. Future Prospects

“If Africans want to stand up and walk, sooner or later they must look elsewhere than to Europe. Europe is undoubtedly not a dying world. But, weary, it now represents the world of declining life and crimson sunsets. Here, the spirit has faded, eaten away by extreme forms of pessimism, nihilism, and frivolity.”

Achille Mbembe, *Out of the Dark Night*, p. 230.

Drawing on the same line of thought expressed by Frantz Fanon in *The Wretched of the Earth*, Mbembe’s *Out of the Dark Night*, calls for “decolonization as a praxis of self-defense and as an experience of emergence and uprising.”³⁸ Postcolonial writers have always called for a certain detachment from the shackles of the ex-colonizer. Subordination and subjugation are soundless weapons that kill cool-bloodedly every human being who is willing to live freely, all the Africans who are willing to “stand up and walk”. The preservation of the two Moroccan cities Ceuta and Melilla (and other islands) under the Spanish occupation, is an extreme form of “pessimism”, “nihilism”, and “frivolity” to subdue and subjugate the non-subjugated. Otherwise, what does it mean to encircle a dozen square kilometers piece of land, in the African continent, hundreds of kilometers away from the European continent, on the Moroccan land, and call it “Spanish”?

In his turn, Frantz Fanon stresses the fact that as African nations, “we must shake off the heavy darkness in which we were plunged, and leave it behind. The new day which is already at hand must find us firm, prudent, and resolute”.³⁹ Subordination

and subjugation to the “West” weakens Africa. These sorts of crippled international relations should be substituted with cooperative and interdependent relations of power that guarantee the African nations a true resurrection and set them free from the tails of colonialism. In this context, Spain seems to be still clinging to this crippled logic of subordination and ‘racial supremacy’.

Last year, Ceuta received a surge of migrant crossings from the Moroccan borders, in which case the Spanish government blamed Morocco for loosening border control on purpose. In the same way, Nasser Bourita, Moroccan Foreign minister, blamed Spain for the diplomatic spat between the two countries and reminded them that “today's Morocco is not that of the past, and Spain needs to understand this”.⁴⁰ Spain and Europe have to accept the fact that the world is changing relentlessly, and today’s geopolitical conditions are not yesterday’s. Every nation is willing to embrace the nations and allies that support its national integrity and foreign policy. One day Africa will find itself obliged to “turn its gaze toward the new. It will have to stage itself and, for the first time, accomplish what has never before been possible. It will have to do this with awareness that it is opening new ages for itself and for the planet.”⁴¹

Recently, the once deaf and stubborn Spanish government has apparently succumbed and opened both ears to the Moroccan diplomatic calls in what concerns his national unity and integrity; thus, following the U.S.A, Germany, France, and the majority of world countries that support the Moroccan right to exert his sovereignty over his historically legitimate land, the southern regions. After a fifteen-month crisis with Madrid, Premier Pedro Sanchez wrote to King Mohamed VI on 14 March 2022 that ““Spain considers the autonomy initiative undertaken by Morocco to be the most serious, realistic and credible basis for resolving the conflict’ over Western Sahara.”⁴² This declaration was welcomed by the Moroccan government and hailed

as a very significant diplomatic gain due to the fact that the whole southern region, which is the same size as the United Kingdom, was formerly ruled by the nation (Spain) as its colonial authority. And because Spain's stance on the subject is widely esteemed, Morocco hopes that other European and Latin American nations would follow Spain's lead.⁴³

What is really interesting and thoughtful in Sanchez's declaration is that he "goes a bit further than France and Germany. The French Foreign Ministry has described the Moroccan plan as "a basis" and not as "the most serious basis" on which to hold "serious and credible talks""⁴⁴

Spain, also, knows well that the contention over the two Moroccan occupied cities will have to be resolved. And, Morocco will never tolerate the occupation of a single spot of its land. Jaime De Pinies once said that "On the day we can restore the sovereignty of Gibraltar to Spain, it would be hard to imagine that the international community will accept that we control the two shores of the Straits."⁴⁵ In the same way, King Hassan II argued that "the day Spain comes into possession of Gibraltar, Morocco will, of necessity, get Ceuta and Melilla. No power can permit Spain to possess both keys to the same straits".⁴⁶ Thus, as a matter of fact, both Morocco and Spain are aware of these conclusions, of these futuristic trajectories that are still conditioned by the factor of time only. Time in this context is, of course, one of the main elements that give meaning to geography as a process of the geopolitical construction of space.

5. Conclusion

The geopolitical construction of space constitutes the main framework for contentious politics and interstate contentions. There is always a certain ideology

behind space construction because when you construct a space, you “intend” to classify, fragment, include, exclude, marginalize, unify, weaken, strengthen ... etc, the different ‘Other’. And since such classifications, fragmentations, inclusions, and exclusions cannot happen unless through the mantle of power, there remains a little room for dialogue and communication simply because power and politics pay no heed for ethics and justice. Undoubtedly, interstate relations are conditioned by the element of power to the highest levels, and no process of the ideological construction of space can happen without power interference. So, this directly affects and impedes interstate collaboration, especially on the geopolitical level.

The Moroccan-Spanish geopolitical relations have witnessed several ebbs and flows. They have gone through different stages that have conditioned and limited their cooperation and outweighed their competition. These stages include the Andalusian period, the post-Andalusian era, Spanish colonialism, and the post-colonial preservation of Moroccan occupied enclaves and islands. Each of these periods contributes its share to the deterioration in interstate relations between these two strategic neighboring countries that are full of qualifications and competences in almost every aspect of life. Benevolent governance on both shores could do wonders to the two peoples as they both reside strategic locations on the world map.

Endnotes

[1] See the preface of the edition by Adela Fábregas (2020), *The Nasrid kingdom of Granada between East and West*, which was translated by Consuelo López-Morillas. It was published within the series of Handbook of Oriental Studies. Section 1 The Near and Middle East, Volume, 148. Leiden: Brill. p. ix.

[2] Said Saddiki (2017). *World of Walls: The Structure, Roles and Effectiveness of Separation Barriers*. London: Cambridge. p. 58.

[3] William C, Atkinson (1960). *A History of Spain and Portugal*. London: Whitefriars press. p.45.

[4] Ibid.

[5] Richard Fletcher (1992). *Moorish Spain*. London: Weidenfeld & Nicolson. p.1.

[6] Louis L'Amour (1985). *The Walking Drum*. New York: Bantam. p.171.

[7] Harold Bloom describes the year (1492) of the expulsion of the Moors and the Jews from Spain as a brutal disaster that was committed by Spanish Catholicism. In forward for *The Ornament of the World: How Muslims, Jews, and Christians Created a Culture of Tolerance in Medieval Spain* by María Rosa Menocal p. xi

[8] Harold Bloom, forward for *The Ornament of the World*. p. xii.

[9] Ibid.

[10] Harold Bloom, forward for *The Ornament of the World: How Muslims, Jews, and Christians Created a Culture of Tolerance in Medieval Spain* by María Rosa Menocal. p. xii

[11] Menocal. *The Ornament of the World*. p.266

[12] Ibid.

[13] Anouar Majid (2004). Book review. *Freedom and Orthodoxy: Islam and Difference in the Post-Andalusian Age*

[14] Morocco Telegraph (June, 21, 2021). "War Crimes: Moroccans Are Still Suffering The Consequences Of Spain's Use Of Chemical Weapons In The Rif". At <https://moroccotelegraph.com/2021/06/3964/war-crimes-moroccans-still-suffer-the-consequences-of-spains-use-of-chemical-weapons-in-the-rif/> accessed on: 28/12/2021. 17:23

[15] Ibid.

[16] Peter Gold (2000). *Europe or Africa: A Contemporary Study of the Spanish North African Enclaves of Ceuta and Melillia*. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press. p. xi

[17] Peter Gold, Ibid.

[18] John Julius Norwich (1998). *The Middle Sea: A History of the Mediterranean*. p. xiv.

[19] William S. Maltby (2009). *The Rise and Fall of the Spanish Empire*. London: Palgrave Macmillan. p.3.

[20] John Agnew (1998, 2003). *Geopolitics: Re-visioning World Politics* (2nd ed.). London: Routledge. p.5.

[21] Ibid.

[22] Griffiths, O’Callaghan, and Roach (2002, 2008). *International Relations: The Key Concepts* (2nd ed.). London: Routledge. p.123.

[23] Knox, Agnew and McCarthy (1989, 2014). *The Geography of the World Economy* (6th ed.). London: Routledge. p. 353.

[24] Mahan, A. (1889, 2009). *The Influence of Sea Power upon History, 1660–1783*. Tucson: Fireship Press. p. I.

[25] Sir Halford Mackinder (1904). “The Geographical Pivot of History”. *The Geographical Journal*, Vol. 170, No. 4, December 2004, pp. 298–32.

[26] Henry Kissinger (1994). *Diplomacy*. New York: Simon & Schuster. p. 82.

[27] Ibid. p. 822.

[28] Ibid.

[29] Zbigniew Brzezinski (1997). *The Grand Chessboard: American Primacy and its Geostrategic Imperatives*. New York: Basic Books. p. xiv.

[30] Ibid.

[31] Geopolitics is criticised for being unable to bracket all the factors that control and contribute to the production of world politics. However, geopolitics remains of crucial importance for every analysis of international relations. And examples of how geographical factors influence state behaviour and state’s foreign policy are plenty. Today, geopolitics has become of much importance as the struggles over space are increasing day after day. It goes without saying that world politics is heavily based on geopolitical assumptions and imaginations. The Middle East, as a rich space and place, has never ceased attracting and creating geopolitical competition, especially between the Orient and the Occident.

[32] Ó Tuathail, Agnew (1992). “Geopolitics and discourse: Practical geopolitical reasoning in American foreign policy”. *Political Geography*, Volume 11, Issue 2, pp. 190-204. At: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/096262989290048X> accessed on 04/02/2022.

[33] John Agnew (1998, 2003). *Geopolitics: Re-visioning World Politics* (2nd ed.). London: Routledge. p.85.

[34] Peter Gold (2000). *Europe or Africa: A Contemporary Study of the Spanish North African Enclaves of Ceuta and Melillia*. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press. p. 144.

[35] Noam Chomsky (2000). *Rogue States: The Rule of Force in World Affairs*. Cambridge, MA: South End Press. p.1.

[36] Griffiths, Martin, Terry O’Callaghan, and Steven C. Roach (2008). *International Relations: The Key Concepts* (2nd ed.). London: Routledge. p.123.

[37] Mohamed Larbi Messari, “The Vivid Memories of Al-Andalus in the Discourse on Dialogue among Civilisations”, <http://www.isesco.org.ma/english/publications/Human%20Civilizations/p32.php>. As cited in Said Saddiki (2017). *World of Walls: The Structure, Roles and Effectiveness of Separation Barriers*. London: Cambridge. p.64.

[38] Achille Mbembe, *Out of the Dark Night*, p. 230.

[39] Frantz Fanon (1963). *The Wretched of the Earth*, Trans. Constance Farrington, New York: Grove. p. 311.

[40] Reuters (May 20, 2021). Morocco blames Spain for spat, says weather caused migrant crisis. At <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/morocco-blames-spain-spat-says-weather-caused-migrant-crisis-2021-05-20/>

[41] Achille Mbembe, *Out of the Dark Night*, p. 230.

[42] Cembrero, Ignacio. (2022, April 15). Spain falls into line with Morocco on the Western Sahara conflict. *Orientxxi.info*. <https://orientxxi.info/magazine/spain-falls-into-line-with-morocco-on-the-western-sahara-conflict,5528> Accessed: 04/05/2022 17:28.

[43] Ibid.

[44] Ibid.

[45] Jaime De Pinies, *La descolonización del Sáhara: Un Tema sin Concluir*. Madrid: Espasa Crónica, 1990, p. 55. Cited in Mohamed Larbi Messari, “The Current Context of a Moroccan Claim to Ceuta and Melilla” (December 2009), as Cited in Said Saddiki (2017). *World of Walls: The Structure, Roles and Effectiveness of Separation Barriers*. London: Cambridge. p. 78.

[46] L’Opinion (26 novembre 1975), cited by Robert Rézette, *The Spanish Enclaves in Morocco*. Paris: Nouvelles Editions Latines, 1976, p. 146, as cited in Said Saddiki (2017). *World of Walls: The Structure, Roles and Effectiveness of Separation Barriers*. London: Cambridge. p. 78.

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